

LIVER HISTOPATHOLOGY OF BLACKCHIN TILAPIA (*SAROTHERODON MELANOTHERON*) AS A BIOMARKER OF ODIMODI RIVER BASIN HEALTH

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17413027>

Abstract

The use of fish Liver as a histological bioindicators is an important environmental biomonitoring tool. Histological biomarkers were adopted to evaluate the health conditions of different organisms and to indicate potential environmental hazards. Histotoxicology is applied as an effective method to evaluate the influence of contaminants and other stressors in surface waters. Therefore, histological changes in the liver tissue of Sarotherodon melanotheron were evaluated and adopted as a bioindicator to measure environmental quality in Odimodi river basin, Delta state Nigeria. A purposive sample of 40 fish was collected from the referenced and experimental sites. It was observed that the referenced site was in good conservation condition, whereas the experimental sites: Location 1, 2 and 3 showed contamination. The fish species collected from experimental sites showed lesions such as degeneration, microvesicular steatosis, and inflammation of the liver; thus, it is statutory to suggest that histological biomarkers be used as the standard bioindicators to measure the environmental status or impact in the environment.

Keywords: *melanotheron, liver; morphology; histological biomarkers; Odimodi*

Introduction

Aquatic organisms are commonly used to evaluate the health status of aquatic organism and their biological responses serve as bio-markers of environmental contaminants. Besides its ecological value, marine water tilapia (*Sarotherodon melanotheron*) fish is also economically important as a food source by low-income families along the Odimodi river shore. *S. melanotheron* is one of the most commonly seen fish in freshwater and marine water used in most ecotoxicological and toxicological studies [1], because it presents a number of characteristics that may make it an appropriate model that can be used as indicator species in biomonitoring programs [2].

After a marine oil spill, monitoring and impact assessment is commonly based on the chemical measurements of petroleum related hydrocarbons in different biota and marine compartments (sediments, water). However, those measurements fail to give information on the bioavailability and bioactivity of the compounds, so histology based ecotoxicological methods are needed as a complement to chemical analysis [3][4].

The incorporation of an effective suite of bioassays and histological biomarkers of exposure can provide insights into the causality of any higher-level adverse effects that may be observed [4]. During recent decades, many studies of oil spills in European waters and elsewhere have clearly demonstrated the potential and usefulness of applying biological-effect techniques in oil spill impact assessments, particularly concerning sublethal and long-term impacts at lower levels of biological organization in organisms, and monitoring the efficacy of remediation [5][6][7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS Study site

Odimodi River Basin (05°21'-43°04'N, 05°25'-46°10'E) is located in Burutu local government of Delta State, Nigeria. It has a tropical Monsoon climate, with a habitable area of about 3 km² and houses a wide variety of habitats such as mangroves, sandbanks, and estuaries (Fig. 1). The bay is 5 m deep, on average, and its water is rich in organic nutrients derived from continental drainage; its bottom is predominantly muddy (NOSDRA, 2019). Odimodi River Basin plays an important role in the regional aquatic ecosystem. Untreated and untreated Industrial activities in this area is responsible for the generation of waste or by product that contains Cadmium (Cd) and Zinc (Zn) [8]. Moreover, this bay has been severely affected by anthropogenic activities over the past 40 years due to build up of materials and contaminants discarded in it have changed its ecosystem [9]. Three Stations within the reach of the communities, station one, station two and station three, which are few meters apart along the creeks of *Odimodi* River were used. This community was chosen because of its oil spillage state for over two years due to oil and industrial activities which have rendered the community prone to contamination within their location.

Study Location

Experiment Site = Odimodi river basin Study stations: (Station 1, Station 2 and Station 3) = **For water and fish sampling**

Reference Site = African Regional Aquaculture Centre (ARAC), Port Harcourt. (Established in 1979 as an African sub-region aquaculture development Centre by FAO/UNDP). Operated since 1987 by the Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research (ARAC/NIOMR). = **For control fish sampling.**

Figure 1 Mapped out study area of Odimodi river basin

3.3 Sample size and Sampling techniques

A purposive sample size determination was used to obtain 10 samples each from three different stations and 10 from the control site (ARAC) with a total of 40 fishes as required for this research, a resource equation formula was applied to check if the specimens are more than necessary for the research work, using degree of freedom (DF) of the specimen sample size which falls within the range of 10 -20.

The degree of freedom was determine using Charan and Kanatharia resource equation method for an experimental animal or sentinel study

The formula is stated thus;

$$Ea = (\text{number of animals in group} \times \text{number of groups}) - \text{number of groups.}$$

Where the number of fish per station for the experiment is ten (10) and the number of stations is three (3), therefore;

$$E = (10 \times 3) - 3$$

$$E = 30 - 3$$

$$E = 27$$

Though the degree of freedom is more than 20, but the number of fish per station is still allowable for the research work.

Fish Sampling

Based on the foregoing, in this study, male specie of *S. melanotheron* fish was used. Outside the fact that the *S. melanotheron* is a dominant fish species in the study area, it's also a widely studied and well documented fish species [10][11].

Fishes were sampled from the three designated stations of experimental site for Gross Anatomical and Histopathological studies. This was done in accordance with USEPA (2015) fish sampling guidelines; 10 fish of the target species were sampled from each station using angling fishing technique. The male species was identified and sorted using Low McConnel method of fish reproduction classification [12].

Fish were dissected; the Liver tissue of each fish was excised. The removed liver tissue was fixed in 10% buffered formalin for 24hr.

Figure 2: *Sarotherodon Melanotheron* Specie

Histological preparations

The Liver tissue was dehydrated in increasing alcohol concentrations, cleared with xylene, and infiltrated using paraffin under laboratory conditions. A sagittal plane sections (4 μm thick) were cut, mounted on glass slides, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin for histological description. Histological changes in gill tissues were classified based on scores from 0 to 3, wherein 0 = no changes, 1 = slight changes, 2 = moderate changes, and 3 = severe changes (Flores-Lopes & Thomaz, 2011). Minor changes do not damage liver tissues, so the restructuring and recovery of liver occur as environmental conditions improves. Among these changes, one finds interstitial edema, leukocyte infiltration, Moderate changes are more severe and affect tissues associated with liver functioning; however, they are reparable, except when vast liver areas are affected or kept under chronic pollution conditions. Regardless of improvements in water quality or lack of exposure to toxic stimuli, severe changes do not allow liver histomorphology to recover; among these changes, one finds steatosis and necrosis of the liver (Nascimento *et al.*, 2012). The histopathologic alterations using the health assessment index (HAI) is based on physical external and internal lesion severity; it classifies changes of each organ based on progressive tissue damage stages for the determination of HAI (Poleksic & Mitrovic-Tutundzic, 1994; Nascimento *et al.*, 2012). The HAI values of each animal were calculated according to the following formula: $\text{HAI} = (1 \times \text{SI}) + (10 \times \text{SII}) + (100 \times \text{SIII})$, wherein I, II and III correspond to the number of changing stages 1, 2 and 3; and S represents the sum of

the number of changes at each particular stage. HAI values ranging from 0 to 10 indicate normal organ functioning, values between 11 and 20 indicate slight changes in the organ, values ranging between 21 and 50 indicate moderate changes in the organ, values ranging from 51 to 100 indicate severe lesions and values greater than 100 indicate irreparable organ lesions (Poleksic & Mitrovic-Tutundzic, 1994).

The percentage of each anomaly observed in the liver tissue of the two fish species collected in each bay was calculated by dividing the number of fish presenting a given anomaly by the total number of examined fish (Table 3).

Environmental Health Status: Furthermore, a modified classification system by Van Dyk *et al.*, (2009a, b) based on a proposed scoring scheme by Zimmerli *et al.*, (2007) was used to evaluate the degree of histological changes. This classification system is based on the calculated mean organ index values:

- I. Class 1 (index value <10): Slight histological alterations.
- II. Class 2 (index value 10-25): Moderate histological alterations.
- III. Class 3 (index value 26-35): Pronounced alterations of organ tissue.
- IV. Class 4 (index value >35): Severe alterations of organ tissue.

Sections were examined using the LEICA ICC50 E microscope (400x).

Statistical analysis

Light microscopy was used to examine the tissues histology. Photomicrographs were taken using the LEICA ICC50 E microscope and at a magnification level of $\times 100$ for clearer visualization. The data obtained from this study was analysed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 to get the descriptive and inferential statistic which includes mean, frequency tables, and bar charts. Inferential analysis such as binomial *t*-test for independent samples and P values was adjusted to minimize type 1 error

RESULTS Water analysis

The DPR (2016) and USEPA (2012) surface water guideline sets the limits for parameters or indicators related to data about the protection of aquatic environment (class 1) DO concentrations should not record less than 5 mg L⁻¹, pH should be kept between 6.5 and 8.5.

Location 1, 2 and 3 showed DO concentrations and pH values within limits determined by the surface water quality guideline mentioned above in all points of collection. On the other hand, Paraty Bay presented turbidity values below the limits established to it. Results of water physical and chemical analysis carried out at the sampling sites are shown in Table 1.

Histological (Alterations) changes in Liver (HA)

We observed significant histological changes in *S. melanotheron* species from the experimental sites. As expected, the analysis of the liver tissue obtained from fish collected at referenced site ARAC showed HA equal to <10 to <20, indicating reversible and slight organ damage. On the other hand, liver tissue obtained from fish collected at experimental sites (odimodi river basin) presented HA between 20> to 100, indicating irreversible organ damage.

The observed histological changes are Glycogen degeneration, Inflammation and steatosis and Microvesicular Degeneration (Plate. 1).

Based on the frequency of histological changes (Table 2), stage III changes were less common in fish species collected in referenced site (ARAC), whereas stage I and II changes were found in the experimental sites (Odimodi river basin).

Table 1. Physical and chemical Analysis of surface water from the collection sites.

Parameters	Location 1	Location 2	Location 3	Guidelines
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
Temp. (°C)	27.80±0.59	27.38±0.46	29.145±0.79	Ambient (<26.0)
pH	5.89±0.27	6.01±0.08	6.65±0.40	6.0 - 9.5
DO (mg/L)	8.15±0.30	8±0.16	5.45±0.44	5.5 -9.5
Conductivity (mS/cm)	280±1.71	281±2.63	307±9.13	180
TDS (mg/L)	663±5.60	660±6.58	641±30.31	500
Salinity (g/kg)	722±5.71	713±17.00	714±25.24	1000
Cd (mg/L)	0.03±0.06	0.03±0.03	0.07±0.081	0.05
Cr (mg/L)	1.14±0.78	3.99±2.69	3.31±2.21	0.003
Cu (mg/L)	0.14±0.28	3.09±3.35	0.98±0.70	0.02
Pb (mg/L)	0.09±0.10	3.09±0.30	0.16±0.13	1
Ni (mg/L)	4.48±3.11	5.98±4.10	6.72±4.48	0.02
PAH (mg/L)	0.002±0.001	0.003±0.002	0.003±0.001	0.001

Table 2. Independent Sample t test comparing the mean Liver Histopathological Organ Indices (I_{org}) of location 1, 2, 3 and the reference site, ARAC.

		Mean organ index(IORG)	STD. Deviation	STD. Error mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
					Lower	upper			
LIVER	ARAC	4.351	4.841	1.53080	-7.363	-.43710	-2.548	9	0.023
	Site 1	9.344	9.548	3.01938	-17.330	-3.6697	-3.478	9	0.017*
	Site 2	11.654	8.054	1.80099	-9.120	-1.5805	-2.971	9	0.008*
	Site 3	10.324	6.734	1.03541	-6.342	-2.4859	-3.232	19	0.006*

Liver Histological Assessment

Plate 1: Photomicrographs (H&E: 400X magnification) of Liver of fishes harvested from ARAC, Site 1, 2 and 3. **A:** Normal Liver histology showing the Hepatocytes (H), Sinusoids (S), Central Vein (CV) and Bile Duct (BD). **B:** Showing Diffuse Glycogen Degeneration with Necrotic Foci (NF) around the Central Vein (CV) and Sinusoids (S). **C:** Showing macrovesicular Fatty Degeneration. **D:** Showing Diffuse Steatosis (ST) with Inflammatory cells Infiltration in the Central Vein (CV).

Table 3: Percentage prevalence of liver histopathology of fishes harvested from **Location 1, 2, 3** and **ARAC**

ALTERATIONS	% PREVALENCE			
	Location (n=10)	1 Location (n=10)	2 Location (n=10)	3 ARAC (n=10)
Circulatory Disturbance (CD)				
Intercellular haemorrhage	10	10	30	0
Regressive Change (RC)				
Intracellular deposits	20	20	30	10
Frank necrosis	0	0	10	0
Fatty change	10	20	40	10
Vacuolation other than steatosis	0	0	10	0
Melano-macrophage centres	10	10	30	10
Foci of Cellular Alteration (FCA)	10	10	10	0
Vacuolated foci				
Necrotic foci	10	10	20	0
Average % Prevalence	8.8	10.0	22.5	3.8

DISCUSSION

The temperature range in all three sites were within the given limits, temperature was not considered a constant in the evaluating surface water due to seasonal changes or fluctuation. Surface water bodies gained oxygen through gaseous exchange from the atmosphere. Aquatic organism especially the fish (*Sarotherodon Melanotheron*) receives oxygen supply from the water and transfer it to their bloodstream through the liver (Francis-Floyd, 2003). The oxygen concentration dissolved in water is known and referred to as dissolved oxygen (DO). DO is an indicator that is commonly used to evaluate and monitor water-quality in coastal and estuarine areas (Jack *et al.*, 2009), causing hypoxic or hyperoxic liver injuries leading to increased blood pressure; the fish liver is influenced by low oxygen levels in the water; this process causes alterations in the liver (Booth, 1979). The mean DO concentrations in Location 1 and 2 were within the recommended limits by DPR and USEPA while that of location 3 failed the given limits. The pH indicator measures the acidity or alkalinity level of the surface water; therefore, which is also an essential indicator to evaluate and control pollution levels, since aquatic metabolism is significantly influence by the water pH (Boyd, 1995). The pH level in this study was significant in Location 1 when compared with Location 2 and 3.

The impact assessment evaluation of study area by NOSDRA, shows that metals presence in the different sites as a result of industrial activities and centers within the area are the main contaminants.

In the water samples, cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni) concentration were observed to be higher than the MATC in site two and site three has Cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), and Nickel (Ni) concentration higher than the MATC (see Table 2 and Table 3), while site one has only chromium (Cr) and Nickel (Ni) were higher than the (MATC) (see Table 4.1).

The concentrations of **Cd** in the water surface body site one, site two and site three were much higher than the MATC of 0.008µg/L at a mean concentration of 0.03µg/L, mean concentration of 0.03mg/L and a mean concentration of 0.07mg/L respectively. Cd is known to be highly soluble in water at intermediate pHs and possibly would have been influenced by the pH values evaluated. Cadmium: is known to cause toxic effects on various organs, such as the kidney, liver, pancreas, testes with serious health issues (death, systemic disease, immunological, neurological, reproductive, developmental, genotoxic, and cancer) (Abdelmoneim et al., 2008).

In this study, evaluated heavy metals: Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Ni and PAH in location 2 and 3 were all beyond their allowable limits except for Pb in location 2, while Location 1 only Cr, Cu, Ni and PAH were above their allowable limits established by DPR and USEPA in Odimodi river basin, thus the histological changes could be caused by the presence of heavy metals in the water. This result confirms the hypothesis and news report that odimodi River basin is at a high risk of chemical contamination and pollution caused by heavy metals.

The general histological structure of the livers of *S. melanotheron* species sampled in this study had similar structures to what was described by Takashima and Hibiya (1995); Van Dyk (2006) and Genten et al. (2009). Liver hepatocytes were hexagonal to oval in shaped and arranged in a hepatic cord structure around blood sinusoids.

The fish specimens Sampled from the sampling trips had mean liver index values which fell into Class 2 (>10) for site 2 and site 3 which means that the liver tissue of those specimens had tissue with moderate histological alterations (Van Dyk *et al.*, 2009). The mean index values for ARAC and site 1 fish specimens fell under class 1 (<10) which indicates slight histological alterations (Plate 1).

All liver alterations observed were regressive changes (RC). This was not an unexpected result as the liver is a major detoxification organ and is involved in the metabolism and excretion of heavy metals and xenobiotics which correlates with study done by Ross *et al.* (1989) describing the liver as the pathway of blood vessels that transport substances from the digestive system, it is the first organ exposed to ingested toxicants. Alterations in the liver is indicative of prior exposure to environmental stressors (Hinton and Laurèn, 1990) which is in line with alterations found in the livers of specimens in this study showing hepatic cord structure disarray; granular degeneration; inter and intracellular deposits; fatty degeneration; increase in connective tissue surrounding central veins; infiltration of mononuclear leukocytes; bile duct wall proliferation; bile duct structural alterations; bile duct granular degeneration; bile duct nuclear alterations (Marchand, 2006).

Alterations found in the liver tissue of specimens in the Okavango study when compared with this present study, had similar intracellular deposits; macrovesicular steatosis; nuclear alterations; necrosis;

inflammatory response; increase in melanomacrophage centers, however the mean liver index values in this study were lower than the values in the Okavango study. Also in a study on *Clarias gariepinus* from the Hartbeespoort Dam (a dam known to be polluted) Botha (2011) found the following alterations in the liver tissue when compared with this present study: Fatty degeneration; glycogen vacuoles; MMCs; necrosis; nuclear alterations; structural alterations; vacuolation; intracellular deposits; hypertrophy and infiltrations of leukocytes which were similar with this study, while the mean liver index values for *C. gariepinus* from the above-mentioned study were 18.2 in the low flow sampling trip and 13.6 in the high flow sampling trip, both liver index values were in Class 2; which is similar to the mean liver index values of site 2 and site 3 in this present study. This means that the liver tissue is still functional but the present results may be a warning sign to future health risks of these fish in these rivers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study showed histological changes in the fish liver, which suggest the contamination and pollution of the assessed sites caused by heavy metals. Histological changes seen in the liver tissue of *S. Melanotheron* could differentiate the pollution level of ARAC (reference site) when compared with Odimodi (experimental site).

The incidence level of liver lesions shows that the fish in Odimodi are experiencing stress disturbance induced by heavy metal contamination of the surface water body. Although further studies are still needed to confirm our results, we can suggest that histological changes in the liver can be considered a useful biomarker to differentiate environmental Pollution status from contamination.

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